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Authors	Rita Meneses, Marialetizia Mari

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Glossary

Acronym	Name
API	Application Programming Interface
CS3	Cloud Services for Synchronization and Sharing
EC	European Commission
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
Eol	Expressions of Interest
EFSS	Enterprise file sync and share
HEP	High-Energy Physics
NREN	National Research and Education Networks
WOPI	Web Application Open Platform Interface

Table 1 Glossary of Acronyms

Executive Summary

CS3MESH4EOSC developed an interoperable, federated platform to easily sync & share data, and deploy applications and software components within the Cloud Services for Synchronization and Sharing (CS3) community. This platform, known as the ScienceMesh, enables researchers, educators, data curators and analysts to retain control over their remote or domestic datasets, while becoming FAIR compatible and integrated with the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). ScienceMesh is interdisciplinary and not specific to any particular research infrastructure. It has a potential to reach a wide audience of stakeholders from both the academia, research and industry.

Chapter 2 presents Expressions of Interest (Eoi) received from stakeholders in embracing the ScienceMesh. The current Eoi stories, which go beyond purely European landscape, demonstrate the intrinsic value and exploitable value of ScienceMesh, which success is based on the federation layer and all the associated data services. The Eois collected come from different types of stakeholder:

- **Industry:** Enterprise file sync and share (EFSS) service providers that had integrated already their functionality in the ScienceMesh;
- **Research:** universities, research institutes and National Research and Education Networks (NREN) interested in adding their EFSS operation layer into ScienceMesh system, as well as cross-sectoral research projects and national initiatives looking forward to using the different data services available
- **Open Science:** European federation networks, non-profit organisations, integrated data service providers, amongst others, interested in both federated layer & data services;
- **Open Source:** software open-source communities looking forward to expanding their user-base and further developing their technology thanks to the ScienceMesh.

The document also describes exploitation and sustainability paths for ScienceMesh assets ensured by **CS3MESH4EOSC project partners**, after the conclusion of the project, described in Chapter 3.

The potential **value of the ScienceMesh for EOSC**, has also been recognised by the European Commission (EC). In 2022 the EC has initiated an EOSC Public Procurement Action of which a call for tenders was published. This call indicates that the sync-and-share service to be proposed need to be integrated with the ScienceMesh.

Chapter 5 also presents insights on how ScienceMesh may contribute to the EOSC's success, mostly by expanding the EOSC user-base with 600K members coming from the CS3 community as well as individual researchers that are not part of any internationally organised community. Chapter 4

enumerates scientific **papers, published during the project timeframe** by CS3MESH4EOSC partners at international conferences focused on technology development (e.g. information systems and digital transformation) and research-field focused (e.g. Physics and Astronomy). To conclude, some **highlights of the ScienceMesh strategic roadmap** along with its critical targets for the next decade are provided in Chapter 6.

1 The ScienceMesh Platform

The Science Mesh is field agnostic, meaning it is a horizontal service that serves multiple science communities at once. This is contrary to many other e-infrastructure services, which are focused on specific science fields. Science Mesh data services can also be integrated with additional science applications developed elsewhere, rendering the overall Science Mesh service offering even more attractive to end-users. This is due to application plugins that ultimately allow for increased capacity for expansion.

Figure 1 ScienceMesh illustrative diagram

2 ScienceMesh offer and Expressions of Interest

The ScienceMesh is a platform under active development at the time of writing this document: while some application components are already integrated in production environments, others are in pre-production stage. The main interoperability platform is in pre-production and is not yet open to the general public. During the development phase, the CS3MESH4EOSC consortium has been focusing on creating a community of potential users of the main interoperability platform, by promoting the ScienceMesh to research communities, open source and service providers to get their interest. The goal is to turn these EoI into leads, backed by a group of champions of ScienceMesh, end-users, adopters or contributors, to accelerate adoption as soon as the tool is open to the public.

In the following sections we document engagement actions leading to creation of Eols for the ScienceMesh. The sections are presented and grouped according to target communities of CS3MESH4EOSC. The institutions, organisations and initiatives listed demonstrate the intrinsic value and exploitable potential of ScienceMesh.

2.1 Industry

Collaboration with the EFSS industry is on the critical path for the development and exploitation of Science Mesh, and EFSS services are a core layer of every ScienceMesh node. They act both as a cloud storage and an integration platform and further enable online and offline file storage, sharing, synchronization and access on a variety of desktop and mobile devices: PCs, tablets or smartphones. EFSS services also provide a plugin extension system which enables developers to add functionality and applications.

The CS3MESH4EOSC project established and maintained collaboration relationships with European Open-Source EFSS industry, namely Owncloud and Nextcloud. Seafile is also another important stakeholder and member of the CS3 community, although technical integration with Seafile has not been pursued yet.

The CS3MESH4EOSC project supported further standardization efforts on OCM (Open Cloud Mesh) by organising OCM workshops with active participation of the EFSS industry:

- During the annual CS3 conferences in the period 2020-2023;
- At a dedicated OCM workshop event¹.

CS3MESH4EOSC launched and funded an initiative to create the OCM Test Suite, and to establish a compatibility matrix between EFSS platforms². This, as well as the technical work on integrating ScienceMesh App in the EFSS platforms, resulted in reporting and fixing interoperability issues between the platforms of the two biggest vendors. Both companies actively engaged in maintaining the OCM 1.0 standard and defining a new version, tagged and released as OCM 1.1.

¹ <https://indico.cern.ch/event/928998/>

² <https://indico.cern.ch/event/1210538/contributions/5208019/>

Organisation	Description	Asset	Description of Interest
	<p>Nextcloud Hub is the industry-leading, fully open-source, on-premises content collaboration platform. Teams access, share and edit their documents, chat and participate in video calls and manage their mail and calendar and projects across mobile, desktop and web interfaces.</p>	<p>ScienceMeshApp integration via ScienceMesh IOP. OCM interoperability</p>	<p>Nextcloud has integrated functionality to enable nodes running its software to become part of the ScienceMesh. Nextcloud accepted pull requests in their core source code which enable a better support of the ScienceMesh App (Nextcloud release 27 and onwards). Nextcloud committed to and fixed OCM 1.0 interoperability issues and undertook work to support protocol extensions defined in OCM1.1.</p>
	<p>ownCloud develops and provides open-source software for content collaboration, allowing teams to easily share and work on files seamlessly regardless of device or location.</p>	<p>CS3 APIs integration with direct Reva support. ScienceMeshApp integration. OCM interoperability.</p>	<p>ownCloud integrated functionality that enables ownCloud-based nodes to become part of the ScienceMesh. ownCloud decided to integrate Reva (a core component of ScienceMesh Interoperability Platform, IOP) and CS3APIs in the core of their new generation product ownCloud Infinite Scale (OCIS). OCIS will benefit directly from OCM compatibility provided by the ScienceMesh IOP.</p>
	<p>Seafile is an open source file sync&share solution designed for high reliability, performance and productivity.</p>	<p>OCM interoperability</p>	<p>Seafile has expressed the will to make its EFSS platform compatible with the latest OCM standard, thus bringing it within reach of the ScienceMesh. The platform was compatible with a previous OCM version.</p>

Table 2 EoI from Industry

2.2 Research

Researchers often need to access and interact with data stored in different clouds, crossing institutional and national boundaries. This requires using different tools, interfaces and authentication methods, which stands in the way of efficient data-based collaboration. Fragmentation of research does not encourage efficient data re-use. Lack of interoperability impacts user experience and

productivity. The possibilities of Interoperability offered by ScienceMesh attracted the interest of several communities of researchers, also beyond Europe, to become part of the federation of cloud storage solutions. Their motivation is to either connect their services in the network or use the data services already available to manage data and collaborate with researchers across borders, institutions, and scientific fields in an easier way.

Organisation	Description	Asset	Description of Interest
Brookhaven National Laboratory	<p>A United States Department of Energy national laboratory. Research at BNL includes nuclear and high energy physics, energy science and technology, environmental and bioscience, nanoscience, and national security.</p>	ScienceMesh federation	<p>Based on ScienceMesh service nodes such as CERNBox, allowing easier collaboration between scientists in the High Energy Physics community and their research centers in North America, Europe and Asia.</p>
 Open Data Systems	<p>Explore the solution provided within the "Open Data Systems" task, based on SCIEBO RDS and RO-crate, to increase ENVRI-FAIR data FAIRness and interoperability.</p>		
 Collaborative Documents	<p>Extend boundaries and capabilities of ESCAPE DIOS (Data Infrastructure for Open Science) in the LOFAR use-case (see below). Prototype and integrate novel approaches to data management such as Data Lakes with Science Mesh and EOSC infrastructures.</p>		
ETH zürich	<p>Public research university in Zürich, Switzerland. ETH Zurich has a world-class reputation in academia and industry, particular in science and technology.[8] It regularly ranks among the top three to five universities in Europe and one of the top 15 to 20 globally.</p>	ScienceMesh federation layer	<p>ETHZ have expressed their desire to turn Polybox, their operated EFSS system, into a ScienceMesh node. They are still testing the onboarding process.</p>
HIFIS HELMHOLTZ FEDERATED IT SERVICES	<p>Helmholtz Federated IT Services (HIFIS) builds and sustains an excellent IT infrastructure</p>	ScienceMesh federated layer & all data services	<p>Interconnect HIFIS federation and ScienceMesh to increase the surface of exposure for</p>

Organisation	Description	Asset	Description of Interest
	connecting all Helmholtz research fields and centres.		HIFIS communities. Become users of the ScienceMesh.
 On-demand Data Transfers	Transfer astronomical data located in different geographical points across the globe and make them accessible in interactive computing environments such as Data Science Environments in ScienceMesh.		
 Data Science Environments	Explore the solution provided within the “Data Science Environments” task, based on JupyterLab, for data displaying/visualizations.		
 Data Science Environments	Use Jupyter service and EFSS based on Nextcloud, integrated into each other with the "Filesystem for Jupyter" software developed in CS3MESH4EOSC		
 Collaborative Documents	The project wants to use embedded tools for easier data citation, collaboration and analysis, while ensuring data security and privacy according to GDPR.		
	The Brazilian NREN. It provides a digital communication and collaboration platform that works to promote and implement innovation in information technology applications. RNP connects more than 4 million Brazilian students, professors and researchers in universities, educational and cultural institutes, research agencies,	ScienceMesh federation layer	RNP have expressed their desire to turn the the RNP-operated EFSS system into a ScienceMesh node. Onboarding is ongoing as of the time of writing.

Organisation	Description	Asset	Description of Interest
	teaching hospitals, technological parks, and hubs		
 Open Data Systems	Promote the ScienceMesh feature of adding work-data via tagging and metadata assignment and publish datasets with PIDs directly on ScienceMesh sites or to external data repositories		
	SUNET' is the Swedish NREN. Its unique data network and secure and stable IT services enable universities and other organizations linked to research or higher education to collaborate nationally and globally.	ScienceMesh federation layer	SUNET expressed their desire to turn the SUNET-operated EFSS (SUNETdrive) into a ScienceMESH node. Onboarding was completed in January 2023, turning SUNET into the first node operated by an insitution outside of the CS3MESH4EOSC project consortium.
	The University of Vienna (German: Universität Wien) is a public research university. The university is associated with 16 Nobel prize winners and has been the home to many scholars of historical and academic importance.	ScienceMesh federation layer	Interest in adding their EFSS service node to the ScienceMesh federation.

Table 3 EoI from Research

2.3 Open Science

The European Commission has placed its Open Science policy high on its digital transformation agenda and supports building EOSC as a cornerstone of this policy. Open Science is essential to leverage the economic and sustainable development of nations. Many benefits may be achieved thanks to it, such as research efficiency, higher levels of quality and integrity, economic developments and a new open eco-system of entities able to face global challenges.

EOSC is envisaged as a trusted digital platform for the scientific community, providing seamless access to data and interoperable services that address the whole research data cycle, from discovery and mining to storage, management, analysis and re-use across borders and scientific disciplines. The CS3MESH4EOSC project was envisioned to support this groundbreaking European goal. The novelty of

the approach proposed by ScienceMesh has also triggered interest from outside Europe, namely from the United States.

Organisation	Organisation Description	Asset	Description of Interest
	<p>A USA non-profit technology organization with a mission to "increase the openness, integrity, and reproducibility of scientific research."</p>	<p>ScienceMesh federated layer & data services</p>	<p>Interest to link COS data-processing capabilities with data available within the ScienceMesh. This would have allowed for cross-Atlantic collaboration, in a scenario akin to the one described above (EGI-ACE). An implementation architecture was developed and jointly agreed upon. Unfortunately, several attempts to secure funding were unsuccessful.</p>
	<p>A European federation of computing and storage resource providers united by a mission of delivering advanced computing and data analytics services for research and innovation.</p>	<p>ScienceMesh federated layer</p>	<p>For secondary use of data to be effective (I.e., researching on data collected by someone else), users need to be able to recombine available datasets (such as available in the ScienceMesh), with EOSC-level data processing capabilities such as the EGI Notebooks facility. This user-driven recombination of assets from EFSS to Jupyter over OCM has been developed through an EGI-ACE grant and shown to be feasible for use in production environments.</p>
	<p>Initiative aiming at developing an infrastructure providing its users with services promoting open science practices</p>	<p>ScienceMesh federated layer & data services</p>	<p>Inclusion of the ScienceMesh in the EOSC Public Procurement Action (see chapter 5 for more info)</p>
	<p>The EUDAT Collaborative Data Infrastructure is one of the largest European infrastructures of integrated data services and resources supporting research in Europe. It is sustained by a network of over 20 research organisations, data and computing centres.</p>	<p>ScienceMesh federated layer</p>	<p>Interest of inclusion of EUDAT's B2DROP, B2SHARE & B2STAGE services as a node within the ScienceMesh</p>

Organisation	Organisation Description	Asset	Description of Interest
	<p>European project that ran pan-European tender and establishing framework agreements with cloud service providers that meet the specific requirements of the research community, saving institutions the time-consuming and complex process of doing this themselves.</p>	<p>ScienceMesh federated layer & data services</p>	<p>EOSC-Future ran a call for European e-Infrastructures where they could build on underpinning resources from OCRE capabilities to build new user-facing services. CS3MESH4EOSC were invited to put in an expression, which was done, collaborating with SUNET and Safespring. The expression was not awarded a grant, however.</p>

Table 4 EoI from Open Science

2.4 Open Source

Open Source, which may be considered part of the 4th sector of the economic landscape, comprises individuals, often connected and facilitated by ad-hoc or charitable communities, playing the roles of the commercial, labor and consumer sectors in varying mixes all at the same time.³ By allowing anybody to access, evaluate and alter the source code, open source encourages greater transparency and security. This increases the software's overall security and stability by allowing developers and security professionals to find and repair bugs and security vulnerabilities more rapidly. Global collaboration and contributions to the creation of software projects are made possible by open source, leading to faster innovation and the creation of more advanced and reliable software.

The CS3MESH4EOSC project engaged in various mutually beneficial open-source collaborations. The ScienceMesh, including its application layer, is powered almost exclusively by open-source third-party software packages from several vendors. Some of those technologies were integrated within the ScienceMesh through efforts of the CS3MESH4EOSC project. In other cases, the project supported contribution to 3rd party open-source packages. Some of those projects (e.g. ScieboRDS) went as far as becoming part of the effort to build the ScienceMesh and integrating one of the Project's tasks. From the perspective of open-source developers of 3rd party packages, this creates additional pathways to expand their user-base and user reach and is an opportunity to support the development of their technology.

Organisation	Description	Asset	Description of Interest
 <p>Open Data Systems</p>	<p>Enhance visibility and reach of RO-Crates technology by its integration in ScienceMesh. This helps to establish RO-Crates as a standard storage format for meta data.</p>		

³ <https://the.webm.ink/consulting-the-fourth-sector>

Organisation	Description	Asset	Description of Interest
	and annotations.		
 Data Science Environments	<p>JupyterLab is considered the gold standard in IDEs for Data Science tasks and interactive processing, where Data Science specialists can do all their work in one tool. So, it is essential that sharing (full CS3API client) and concurrent editing features are available in this environment. On the other hand, Data Science Environments are tightly integrated with the EFSS storage in ScienceMesh to support complete research and Data Science workflows using existing collaboration tools.</p>		
 Collaborative Documents	<p>Onlyoffice is a powerful MS-office compatible editor for all kinds of office documents. It enables users of EFSS systems collaborative online editing. The integration in the ScienceMesh makes it available to a greater audience.</p>		
 On-demand Data Transfers	<p>Rclone is an opensource tool to copy data to and from 40+ cloud services. As such, it has gathered quite a large following. The improvements made to Rclone and which were funded by the CS3MESH4EOSC project do not only benefit the ScienceMesh but a lot of other applications as well. This will further expand the applicability of Rclone. The CS3MESH4EOSC project also directly funded</p>		

Organisation	Description	Asset	Description of Interest
			some Rclone features required to implement Science Mesh On-Demand Data Transfers workflows.
 Data Science Environments	<p>The VOIS library is used inside the European Commission BDAP Cloud Platform to communicate scientific results to a wider audience. After having passed the IP clearance and security checks phases, the library is ready for publication as open source on the https://code.europa.eu/repository/platform. Interest has been acknowledged for the library and on the products, it can help to create both from EC directorates (Eurostat, DG-Agri, etc.), and from other european institutions. The library and the dashboards created with it will be presented at the "Project Managers and Business Analysts Community of Practice event" organized by the Directorate-General for Innovation and Technological Support of the European Parliament in Luxembourg.</p>		

Table 5 EoI from Open Source

3 Sustainability paths for CS3MESH4EOSC assets

In the section below we present the exploitation and sustainability paths for ScienceMesh assets ensured by CS3MESH4EOSC project partners.

3.1 ScienceMesh Federation Layer

The ScienceMesh Federation Layer allows users at different sites to easily share and exchange data. It is also a technical foundation that allows users to reach and interact with remote applications in an interoperable way. This is possible thanks to a set of interoperability protocols and Application

Programming Interfaces (APIs). Examples of possible and intended usage of Science Mesh Federation layer by CS3MESH4EOSC partners are listed below.

By joining the ScienceMesh federation, **CERN** aims to leverage its expertise and resources to facilitate interdisciplinary research and promote open access to scientific data through the CERNBox service. CERN seeks to strengthen global scientific cooperation, encourage knowledge-sharing and collaboration in the broader High Energy Physics community (HEP). The HEP community collaborating with CERN consists of some 600 research institutes around the world. International collaboration is one of the keys to support CERN's mission and to contribute to solving some of the most pressing challenges facing our society. In particular, CERN's groundbreaking research in particle physics and its world-renowned particle accelerator, the Large Hadron Collider (LHC), have propelled humanity's understanding of the fundamental building blocks of the universe.

SWITCH is committed to integrating the ScienceMesh App into its ownCloud based service SWITCHdrive. This service is used by most institutions in Swiss Higher Education and has about 30.000 active users, a heterogeneous group of researchers, teachers, students and faculty employees. The seamless sharing with partners around the world will be the main use case for those users and will be a great benefit to them. By adding SWITCHdrive within the ScienceMesh, all SWITCH active users will have access to the application platform provided by the Project. This will allow Swiss research communities to achieve higher efficiency in collaboration.

The CS3MESH4EOSC Czech partner **CESNET**, an association of universities of the Czech Republic and the Czech Academy of Sciences, operates and develops the national e-infrastructure for science, research and education which encompasses a computer network, computational grids, data storage and a collaborative environment. Its cloud service called "CESNET's ownCloud" serves over 20.000 users all around the Czech Republic. The ScienceMesh will significantly improve user comfort relating to data sharing across European research institutions, by supporting easy sharing of resources. For CESNET, data infrastructure is a crucial part of its ecosystem of services, and it has plans to continue operation of a sync and share service in the long term. CESNET's users will especially benefit from the results of the Data Science Environments and On-demand Data Transfers tasks.

CUBBIT is an Italian SME with over 5.000 customers, which provides a distributed cloud, an enabling technology that transfers data sovereignty and control back to users, guarantees the highest level of security and privacy by design, reduces environmental impact, and offers economically competitive services. Cubbit users are currently uploading 1PB per month in the distributed Cubbit storage cloud.

The Cubbit storage cloud provides Amazon S3 Compatible APIs, and can connect to ScienceMesh via an S3-like API. This allows CUBBIT nodes to become storage providers in ScienceMesh. Conversely, ScienceMesh sites could voluntarily choose to contribute to the CUBBIT network by providing additional space to Cubbit users, on a basis of a peer-to-peer exchanges of services.

3.2 Data Science Environments

The ScienceMesh Data Science Environments integrate interactive computing platforms based on Jupyter notebooks with the EFSS storage and allow the remote access to analysis notebooks.

Figure 2 The ScienceMesh "Data Science Environments" logo

3.2.1 Core Data Science Environments - JupyterLab extension (CS3API4LAB)

The core component of ScienceMesh Data Science Environments is a JupyterLab extension, CS3API4LAB, which integrates JupyterLab with ScienceMesh.

Figure 3 JupyterLab Logo

Two important aspects in the sustainability of this extension can be taken for granted and do not require additional actions:

- ScienceMesh Federation Layer (which provides CS3APIs and OCM used by the extension to provide sharing and collaboration features in a multi-cloud environment) – the sustainability and governance of this layer is provided by the ScienceMesh;
- A separate server infrastructure is not required - when users install the JupyterLab extension, it's typically run on their existing Jupyter server. From the perspective of the JupyterLab extension's users and developers, there isn't a need to provide additional server infrastructure.

Maintaining the long-term sustainability of the JupyterLab plugin (as an open-source product) involved a blend of technical excellence, community engagement, and strategic planning. The following steps have been taken and planned to ensure keeping CS3API4LAB running after the end of the project:

- **The Scope and Goals** have been clearly defined (the purpose of your plugin, its functionality, and its benefits for users). The value proposition of CS3API4LAB extension:
 - Seamless integration with Jupyter notebooks;
 - Sharing and collaboration features in JupyterLab environment;
 - Easy configuration of integration with EFSS systems;
 - Good performance even with large files or notebooks;
 - High level of support and community around the open-source project;
 - Highly specialized knowledge of the core development team in this field (for other players the barriers to entry are quite high, requiring significant technical expertise and resources).
- **High-Quality Code and Documentation:** best practices for coding used in the development and ensuring the code is well-documented help maintain code quality but also makes it easier for newcomers to understand and contribute;
- **Regular Maintenance and Updates:** keeping the plugin compatible with the latest versions and updates of JupyterLab will be aided by setting up automated testing and continuous integration/continuous delivery (CI/CD) pipelines;
- **Community Building:** community participation is encouraged by making the contribution process transparent and welcoming (creating a contributing guide);
- **User Support:** installation instructions and troubleshooting tips have been provided in the documentation. As a part of preparing the scope for future development (to prepare proposals for funding and sponsorship), user issues and feedback will be addressed via GitHub issues;
- **Seeking Feedback:** user feedback has been continuously collected and incorporated into the project and will be in the future (as explained above), as user needs can change over time;
- **Promoting the Plugin:** the CS3 community and the broader Jupyter community have been reached via blog posts, talks at conferences (like JupyterCon), and by sharing the work related to ScienceMesh Data Science Environments on social **media**.

AILLERON, a Polish software company and partner in CS3MESH4EOSC, as the main driver of Data Science Environments and the developer of the CS3API4LAB Jupyterlab extension, intends - along with

its daughter-company Software Mind - to exploit potential revenue streams, lead efforts seeking funding and sponsorship, as well as other activities related to product sustainability listed above – and based on this will be continuing the development of the CS3API4LAB Jupyterlab extension.

- **Potential Revenue Streams** will include:
 - Paid support and services: Offering paid support, consulting, and professional services for CS3API4LAB extension. This can include installation, configuration, troubleshooting, and training services;
 - Software development services: Offering application services including integration, dev-ops and adding new specialized functionalities CS3API4LAB extension, as well as in related areas (data science environments, cloud integration, hybrid cloud, Knowledge Graph, Microsoft Graph).

Seeking Funding and Sponsorship: Ailleron / Software Mind will lead efforts to seek external funding/grants for further development of CS3API4LAB extension as well as for maintenance, and promotion: by participating in calls in Horizon Europe and other funding programs, to fund development of new advanced/innovative features of CS3API4LAB extension, based on the feedback collected and analysis of current trends (Data Lakehouse, Data Mesh, Knowledge Graph); **CERN**, based on their active engagement in shaping the CS3API4LAB Jupyterlab extension and tests in CERN environment (the extension has been developed in close collaboration with CERN) plans to include the extension in SWAN (CERN’s Jupyter notebooks service provided by CERN IT department) by end of 2023 or beginning of 2024 as this is bundled with the deployment of JupyterLab.

PSNC also intends to adopt the CS3API4LAB plugin in selected educational activities (for details see chapter 3.2.3 EFSS Filesystem for Jupyter below).

3.2.2 VOIS (Voilà Simplification library)

The VOIS library has many functions for the easy creation of complex geospatial visualizations (like bi-variate and tri-variate choropleth maps for vector data, or fast display of multi-terabytes raster datasets). It has just passed all the preliminary steps needed for the publication as Open Source in the <https://code.europa.eu> repository.

Figure 4 Voilà & VOIS logos

After the successful Intellectual Property Clearance phase, also the Security Assessment phase was recently passed. It will soon be published as full Open Source. Just after the publication, it will be added to the PyPI repository, so that it will be possible to install VOIS on any Python environment. JRC is also planning to test its usage in Microsoft Azure and in the Huggingface cloud system. The library is currently used to build many dashboards inside the **Joint Research Centre (JRC)**, the European Commission's science and knowledge service which employs scientists to carry out research in order to provide independent scientific advice and support to European Union policy.

It is being exploited by The JRC's Big Data Analytics Platform (BDAP) members and by other colleagues who followed one of the training courses that SoftwareMind provided in recent months (the last one was a full day on the 5th of May, and it saw the presence of more than 35 JRC colleagues). This training on VOIS and Voila⁴ is now part of an official learning path in the Commission EU Learn portal, and will be repeated regularly twice per year.

JRC intends to keep developing the VOIS library by adding widgets and code snippets that can be useful to speed-up the creation of impactful Voila' dashboards to present the results of scientific research to a wider public, as to make it a complete framework for scientific web-application development. JRC is providing user support, promoting VOIS and actively building the community. Significant interest has been acknowledged regarding the library and the products it can help to create, both from EC directorates (Eurostat, DG-Agri, etc.) as well as other European institutions. The VOIS library and the dashboards created with it were presented at the "Project Managers and Business Analysts Community of Practice event" organized by the Directorate-General for Innovation and Technological Support of the European Parliament in Luxembourg.

AILLERON / Software Mind will include Voila and VOIS in exploitation and further development of CS3API4LAB JupyterLab extension (the core component of Data Science Environments - described in chapter 3.2.1 above), as well as in other Data Science projects.

At **CERN**, Voila dashboards are already available in SWAN, and are being used by some users. The expectation is that VOIS is widely deployed and becomes available to anyone willing to use it.

PSNC uses Voila in their educational projects (also evaluated JupyterLite) and intends to use the VOIS library to create advanced Voila dashboards in this context.

⁴ The course user-guide: https://vois.readthedocs.io/en/latest/1_intro.html

3.2.3 EFSS Filesystem for Jupyter

The solution for backend filesystem integration developed by PSNC as part of the ScienceMesh Data Science environments: “EFSS Filesystem for Jupyter”⁵ offers two alternative solutions for accessing files:

- *sync* - synchronize files with EFSS client;
- *fuse* - FUSE mount EFSS files via WebDAV.

The backend Jupyter-EFSS filesystem integration is made available as open source.

PSNC intends to enhance the development of “EFSS Filesystem for Jupyter” after the project concludes, as PSNC is actively engaged in multiple initiatives that utilize this extension. At the time of writing, the extension is being utilized by initiatives like the European project 'Up2DigiSchool' and the Polish platform 'PIONIER Research and Classroom'. Additionally, the European project 'AI-Entr4Youth' is contemplating adopting it for their users.

AILLERON / Software Mind plans to use “EFSS Filesystem for Jupyter” integrated with the CS3API4LAB extension for backend filesystem integration – as part of a wider plan for future development of additional file access patterns and integration options (Data Lakehouse, Data Mesh, Distributed Cloud, Knowledge Graph).

3.3 Open Data Systems

Open Data Systems allow the user to add metadata and publish datasets with persistent identifiers directly on the Science Mesh sites or to external data repositories.

Figure 5 The ScienceMesh "Open Data Systems" logo

The ScieboRDS⁶ system started as a project funded by the German Research Foundation (DFG) and developed by the **University of Münster (WWU)**. It has been adopted and further developed by the ScienceMesh as its flagship open data appliance.

⁵ <https://github.com/sciencemesh/filesystem-for-jupyter/>

⁶ <https://www.research-data-services.org/>

Figure 6 ScieboRDS logo

The **ScieboRDS project** has funds left for another 21 months after the conclusion of CS3MESH4EOSC, and there could be the possibility of a follow-up project. WWU has interest in growing the community of adopters and plans to integrate it as a core service of Sciebo by the end of the year. WWU views ScieboRDS as a service that will live on for years to come (powered by its own community of stakeholders). This also holds true for resources like the website/documentation. A rebranding of ScieboRDS is also envisaged in the near future, as it grows out of the local scope of the Sciebo platform.

CERN is also evaluating the adoption of this RDS system for its own research activities. The system has, in the meantime, also been deployed at **SUNet** and **SURF**, where it is integrated with their EFSS nodes and their local digital repositories.

3.4 Collaborative Documents

This service allows cross-federation collaboration on content in real time: simultaneous editing of documents, commenting, versioning, in safe EU-based cloud environments.

Figure 7 The ScienceMesh "Collaborative Documents" logo

The prototypes which were developed as part of the Collaborative Documents task rely on the OCM protocol for the federation layer (see above), and on the Web Application Open Platform Interface (WOPI) protocol, an open standard developed by Microsoft to support Office applications and adopted by several application vendors, including Collabora and Onlyoffice.

The CodiMD prototype leveraged on the capabilities of WOPI to make the application backend interoperable with ScienceMesh setups, and this extension is already used in production at **CERN**. Another essential component is the Reva daemon, which is maintained by CERN as the core of the

CERNBox production service. The front-end integration, especially the “Open with” function has to be maintained as a joint effort of the institutions participating in the ScienceMesh.

Integration of Collabora and Onlyoffice within the ScienceMesh is thus ensured to be sustainable in the long term: since the WOPI protocol is now implemented by the applications in question, it can be assumed that they will work in the ScienceMesh without any further work from the consortium other than compliance with new protocol versions.

3.5 On-demand data transfers

The “On-demand data transfers” support file transfer between EFSS storage endpoints of the

ScienceMesh nodes.

Figure 8 The ScienceMesh "On-demand data transfers" logo

There are two types of on-demand data transfers:

- **Ad-hoc data transfers** that focus on data transfers between individual researchers;
- **Managed data transfers** that are managed by organized scientific communities.

Both types of data transfers rely on open-source software and open standards that are used in a much wider community than the CS3MESH4EOSC project. They were already existing before the start of this project and will continue to exist after the CS3MESH4EOSC project has ended. There is no dependency on these open-source tools and open standards on the CS3MESH4EOSC project. An attempt will be made at obtaining funding to maintain and, if possible, further develop the data transfer software.

SURF, the collaborative organisation for IT in Dutch education and research, is involved in several High-Energy Physics (HEP) initiatives where the managed data transfers tools Rucio and FTS are used. Rucio has been developed by the ATLAS LHC experiment several years ago, as a tool for scientific data management, and has since then been adopted by other scientific communities as well, like CMS and also the astronomy community (ESCAPE). FTS is the file transfer service that orchestrates data transfers which has been used by the HEP (ATLAS, ALICE, LHCb and CMS) community for more than 15 years. EGI also runs an FTS service for their users.

For ad-hoc data transfers, Rclone is used. This is a widely used tool to manage files on cloud storages. Rclone integration relies on the Reva interoperability platform, which is currently used and maintained

at CERN. The open standards used are OIDC and WebDAV. The WWU intends to use the Rclone integration for the *HPC.NRW* project, where it is currently the best candidate for a solution for data transfer between different computing centres.

3.6 Sciencemesh.io website

The *sciencemesh.io*⁷ website is the main point of access to the Science Mesh product and thus a very important asset which should not only be kept “alive” but also undergo continuous evolution. The consortium identified the following costing items with regards to this point:

- DNS domain - the domain is owned presently by CERN, but can be transferred to any other legal entity if required. The cost is marginal (less than 100 EUR/year) and is currently borne by CERN;
- Content management system - the Project website relies on a Git repository (currently hosted on GitHub⁸) for its content backend, with automatic re-generation being triggered whenever there is a change. This repository can be moved anywhere else at anytime (e.g. GitLab⁹, Codeberg¹⁰, etc.);
- Hosting of the site - the resulting website HTML files are currently hosted by CERN, on its PaaS infrastructure. Once again, this could be easily moved elsewhere (e.g. GitHub) if needed. The cost is once again marginal (< 100 EUR);
- Certificate - a LetsEncrypt¹¹ a certificate is being used, which means this comes at no cost.

As for the *developer.sciencemesh.io* sub-website (technical documentation), it is currently deployed on Netlify¹², on a free tier setup. This could be easily transferred to the PaaS platform of CERN or any other suitable partner (or GitHub, alternatively). There are no costs associated besides the domain name, which is already factored in above.

In summary, the actual cost of providing and maintaining the *sciencemesh.io* website and associated documentation site, from an infrastructure point of view, can be considered residual, amounting to fixed costs inferior to 200 EUR/year. This means that, from the logistical point of view, this activity's

⁷ <https://sciencemesh.io/>

⁸ <https://github.com>

⁹ <https://gitlab.com/>

¹⁰ <https://codeberg.org/>

¹¹ <https://letsencrypt.org/>

¹² <https://www.netlify.com/>

sustainability is easily assured. Maintaining the websites amounts to more than having them online, however, and will require regular updates and curation. The CS3MESH4EOSC consortium will discuss and allocate this point as part of the activities of the ScienceMesh Steering Group.

3.7 CS3MESH4EOSC website

The CS3MESH4EOSC website will be available online for 3 years after the end of the project. Trust-IT Services will ensure free access to information about the services, the demos and use-cases and minimal updates in the news sections. The website will be maintained up with minimal technical effort with no functional evolution. Credentials to access & manage the platform could be given to other subjects indicated by the EC.

4 Scientific/White Papers

The Communication and Marketing activities of the project followed a content-driven approach, meaning that the promotion efforts focus on producing valuable and informative content. One of the key strategies used is collaborating on specialized content. The aim has been to establish engagement with the specific target audiences who are interested in the ScienceMesh. In this way, the project aims to raise awareness and generate interest in the ScienceMesh among the relevant stakeholders in the field.

DOI/Link	Publication date	Authors	Title
doi.org/10.1051/epjconf/202024507041	November 2020 (EPJ Web of Conferences)	Hugo González Labrador, Jakub T. Mościcki, Massimo Lamanna and Alberto Pace	Increasing interoperability for research clouds: CS3APIs for connecting sync&share storage, applications and science environments.
zenodo.org/record/5083268#.ZGT3ruxBxTZ	June 2021 (ECIS 2021)	Angelo Romasanta; Jonathan Wareham (ESADE)	FAIR DATA through a federated cloud infrastructure exploring the ScienceMesh.
https://zenodo.org/record/7886755	May 2, 2023 (Horizon Results Booster)	Sasha Woods; Sona Arasteh; Eliza Papaki; Gideon van den Berg	Exemplary Digital Services Enabling Open Science: Cos4Cloud, TRIPLE and CS3MESH4EOSC.
Awaiting publication	March 3, 2023 (EUNIS 2023)	Holger Angenent, Daniel Müller, Raimund Vogl	Bringing HPC Clusters into the ScienceMesh.

Table 6 List of Papers by CS3MESH4EOSC

5 ScienceMesh in the EOSC Marketplace

The ScienceMesh has had a very different history than other e-infrastructures involved with EOSC. Unlike the latter, which came into being starting from (EU-)funded projects, the ScienceMesh evolved from a grassroots community of organisations running sustainable EFSS services for their own users,

who decided to offer added value to their users by federating their services and facilitating access to research application services. This has led to the creation of the CS3MESH4EOSC project.

EFSS services have become quite successful over the last decade or so, both on-premises and in the cloud. The EFSS market has been growing ever since these services appeared. Currently, EFSS services are a multi-billion-dollar business and are ever growing.

This phenomenon is not limited to the industrial sector - the same is true for science, research and education as well. Surveys held among the attendants of the CS3 conferences revealed that hundreds of thousands of users are served by the EFSS services represented at the conference. In March 2023, this meant more than 600.000 users. The reason for their success is obvious: they provide low-threshold access to data and easy pathways to share it with others: *“Wherever you go, your data goes with you, either in the cloud or synced to your laptop. Moreover, your data is also accessible from mobile clients.”* This is very appealing to a large segment of the research user market, especially those who are not especially tech-savvy. Over the years, EFSS services in the business domain did not stick to just sync and share, but they we also integrated with all kinds of business applications. For science and education, a similar phenomenon happened: here, EFSS services were integrated with science applications, like Jupyter notebooks, the Open Science Framework (OSF), R-Space and learning platforms such as Moodle. All these add-ons make these services even more attractive to users.

5.1 Horizontal service architecture

EOSC envisages user communities that are organised to some extent and already have an e-infrastructure at their disposal with a portal and other services. Their focus is on serving users in a particular science domain. The ScienceMesh, however, in its essence, has a much more general nature than these e-infrastructures focussed on a science domain – the ScienceMesh is science agnostic and is there to serve the entire community. Moreover, the group which is bootstrapping the mesh is composed of NRENs, national e-infrastructures, university compute centres and ICT service providers for academia. Those organisations are, in general, already serving science at large and not targeting any particular discipline. For this reason, we believe that the ScienceMesh qualifies as a **horizontal service** in the EOSC architecture and is an asset to EOSC.

5.2 Science Mesh as an EOSC service

However, there is an additional benefit to the ScienceMesh joining EOSC: as mentioned above, EOSC seems to be focusing on user communities which are capable of providing their own e-infrastructures. However, there are a lot of individual researchers and research groups out there that are not part of any internationally organised community, let alone have their own e-infrastructure. They are also collaborating with other researchers across organisational and national boundaries. This is where the ScienceMesh can work its magic, by also connecting these users to FAIR data repositories and other research products in EOSC, through none other than their own “home” EFSS service.

EFSS services focused on research and education reach several hundreds of thousands of users, which is only a fraction of the 1.89 million researchers estimated to be active in Europe right now. There is thus a huge future growth potential to be exploited in the coming years.

The potential value of the ScienceMesh for EOSC has also been recognized by the European Commission. In 2022, the EC initiated an EOSC Public Procurement Action, of which a call for tenders was published on December 20st 2022. The title of Lot 3 of this procurement is “Managed Collaborative Data Platform, Interactive Data Analytics Platform and Visualization Services for the EOSC Exchange”. In this lot, the EC requests a sync-and-share service with an interactive notebooks service and a managed file transfer service. The EC requires the service to be integrated with the ScienceMesh.

In general, the EOSC technical specifications and interoperability guidelines are still being defined. When including the ScienceMesh into the EOSC infrastructure the consortium will have to consider the specifications and guidelines at their present state.

6 Current Stage and Next Steps by 2030

Maintaining the various ScienceMesh essential operations running after the current funding cycle terminates is critical. Fortunately, the structure of the ScienceMesh allows for lean operation, with minimal administrative and technical costs. This inherent design will likely be instrumental in ensuring sustainability of the ScienceMesh. That said, further investment is needed to:

- 1) *Bridge* the ScienceMesh into early adopter communities, enrol and deploy all partner nodes, and publish user stories;
- 2) *Grow* the ScienceMesh by establishing strategic partnerships with funding agencies, creating a governing body, enrolling more nodes, and maximising the ultimate value extracted by end-users;

- 3) *Sustain* the ScienceMesh and ensure that it is a viable platform for FAIR data and Open Science, enabling collaborative research towards solving increasingly complex societal challenges, and kickstarting interoperability across cloud providers.

Herewith a summary of the ScienceMesh strategic roadmap, highlighting critical targets for the next decade. For a more detailed discussion, please see *D5.5: Business impact assessment and roadmap for effective management*.

To truly unleash the collaborative potential of the ScienceMesh in the future and ensure its long-term sustainability, three main categories for investment were identified that can be organized along two axes (Figure 9).

1. **Essential operations** of the ScienceMesh constitute the core of the framework for future sustainability. These essential operations include the Steering Committee, software maintenance, DevOps, and a Service Desk. Importantly, a distinction needs to be made between these essential operation elements and others in the sustainability framework; the essential operations should not be considered components of ScienceMesh *sustainability*, but instead, the very *existence* of the Science Mesh. Without sufficient maintenance of the essential operations, the Science Mesh will cease to provide its service. As such, it is essential that these elements are maintained while funding is secured to pave the road for genuine sustainability of the Project.
2. **Priority investments** for the ScienceMesh can be categorized along the axes of (1) external adoption or internal/technical, (2) service providers/research infrastructures or users/scientific communities. Firstly, new nodes should be enrolled into the ScienceMesh. Expanding and integrating new cloud services to enable interoperability among them will be an important objective for sustainability. Crucially, this onboarding process should be intuitive and frictionless. Secondly, empowering service providers within the ScienceMesh to manage their respective nodes is a valuable target. Technical capabilities can be improved through tools developed by the ScienceMesh designed to, for example, monitor the real-time impact of the ScienceMesh and identify emerging issues, through a user-friendly dashboard. Thirdly, engagement with user communities is of the utmost importance. Many connected nodes would be purposeless without researchers and end-users themselves actively using the ScienceMesh. Thus, maximizing the use of the ScienceMesh through carefully designed and disseminated training materials will play an important role in securing a highly used and sustainable ScienceMesh. Finally, to stay relevant with the ever-evolving state-of-the-art data

science and machine learning applications, the ScienceMesh should consider developing new capabilities. Indeed, despite the current novel applications built into the ScienceMesh architecture, investment should be dedicated to integrating new computational tools as they are developed.

3. **Long-term sustainability** targets can be also constructed for some previously mentioned priority investments. For example, tight integration with the larger EOSC initiative, and analysing/overcoming the various barriers to connecting to the ScienceMesh will play an important role in the sustainable involvement of new nodes. With respect to the development of admin capabilities, ScienceMesh partners should ensure that healthy relationships with cloud software vendors such as NextCloud, OwnCloud, and SeaFile are maintained, ensuring frictionless communication channels and the collaborative development of admin capabilities. Sustainable user engagement requires a transparent integration within EOSC and the continuous monitoring of key metrics (see *D5.5: Business impact assessment and roadmap for effective management*).

Figure 9 Framework to understand the sustainability directions of the ScienceMesh (taken from *D5.5: Business impact assessment and roadmap for effective management*).

7 Conclusion

The development of the ScienceMesh is the emanation of collaborative **experience** stemming from the grassroots CS3 Community and its attendant fora and communications platforms, including CS3MESH4EOSC project members - all also members of CS3. The ScienceMesh idea came from an opportunity window that came from the cloud services market, to make European Cloud Computing part of the top list of cloud service providers in terms of infrastructure and EFSS. The exploitation of results from already existing technologies, majority in Open Source, is fundamental for the CS3MESH4EOSC work.

CS3MESH4EOSC now leaves a legacy to researchers, software development professionals, cloud service providers, open-source community, as well as organisations from the private sector. The ScienceMesh services are on the track to be made available to all users and applications, thanks to the federated infrastructure created, where users have the possibility themselves to customise the mesh applications, by adding more nodes and technologies.

The Eol presented in this document (from industry, research, open source and open science representatives), as well as the future plans from CS3MESH4EOSC partners, prove the usefulness, exploitation and benefits that the ScienceMesh platform can bring to the scientific collaboration and to a borderless European research environment. These Eol scenarios open doors to new opportunities for either collaboration and further developments of the ScienceMesh. The inclusion of the ScienceMesh into EOSC is also foreseen, as soon as more technical details regarding the EOSC foundation are defined.

To conclude, the CS3MESH4EOSC project has developed and consolidated the founding pillars of the ScienceMesh which, when in operation and open to the public, will advance the principles of the EU Cloud Initiative and support the “European Digital Transformation of Business” as referred in the “Europe’s Digital Decade: digital targets for 2030¹³” communication.

¹³ Source: https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/priorities-2019-2024/europe-fit-digital-age/europes-digital-decade-digital-targets-2030_en